

Scaling of Energy Constraint and MaxEnt for the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis Distributions

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 6, 2025

In (1), (2) we used a scaling of the energy constraint in a statistical problem with respect to $T \rightarrow T + dT$ to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis distributions without recourse to MaxEnt or reaction balance. Here, we try to show the connection between the scaling of the energy constraint with these other approaches.

Scaling Approach Applied to an Energy Constraint

In (1), (2) we used a scaling approach, applied to the energy constraint through $T \rightarrow T + dT$, to find the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) and Tsallis distributions. In the MB case, we used:

$$E_{ave} = \left\{ \int c_1 \sqrt{e} de e p(e/T) \right\} / \left\{ \int c_1 \sqrt{e} de p(e/T) \right\} \quad ((1))$$

We worked in 3-dimensions, hence $\sqrt{e} de$ and used the approximation that e ranges from 0 to infinity. Given that $p(e/T)$, p being unnormalized, we used the variable $y=e/T$ so that $e \rightarrow T y$ leads to:

$$E_{ave} = T * \text{Number} \quad ((2))$$

As a result, Number is the same for T and $T+dT$, but given that the integral in y used to calculate Number may be rewritten again in terms of e, T , one may replace T with $T+dT$ and argue that the coefficient of dT should be 0. In (1), it was shown that for the Maxwell-Boltzmann energy constraint this leads to the differential equation:

$$N y dp/dy - p y - y y dp/dy = 0 \quad ((3))$$

Here N is a number which requires knowledge of $p(e)$ and its integral so ((3)) is a little more complicated than a simple differential equation for which N as a given number. Nevertheless, we were able to solve ((3)) in (1) and find the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution solution:

$$p(e) = \exp(-e/T) \quad (p(e) \text{ unnormalized}) \quad ((4))$$

As a result, MaxEnt and reaction balance were not used.

In (2), we applied the same reasoning to the Tsallis energy constraint:

$$E_{ave} = \left\{ \int c_1 \sqrt{e} de p(e/T) \text{ power } q e \right\} / \left\{ \int c_1 \sqrt{e} de p(e/T) \right\} \text{ power } q \quad ((5))$$

This led to the differential equation:

$$0 = N q y dp/dy - p \text{ power } q y = q y y dp/dy p \text{ power } q-1 \quad ((6))$$

Again N is not an a priori given number, but one may still obtain an solution.

We suggested that p is a power law type function:

$$p(e) = B \text{ power } b = (1 + f(q)e/T) \text{ power } b \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{For } q=1, p(e) = \exp(-e/T) \quad ((8))$$

Using the differential equation and B as a linear variable, we argued that the powers of all three terms must be the same in order to have the terms add to 0. This yields:

$$b = 1/(1-q) \quad ((9a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(q) = -(1-q) \quad \text{for } p(e, q=1) = \exp(-e/T) \quad ((9b))$$

As a result, one is able to find the Tsallis distribution $(1 - (1-q)e/T) \text{ Power } 1/(1-q) \quad ((10))$ without using MaxEnt.

We note that for the Kaniadakis case, the energy constraint is that of the Maxwell-Boltzmann case and that the ensuing differential equation yields a Maxwell-Boltzmann solution.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Case and a Link Between Reaction Balance, MaxEnt and Scaling

One may take the last term in ((3)) and integrate by parts to convert it into:

$$2.5 y p \quad ((11))$$

Note: $N=3/2$ for $p=\exp(-e/T)$ as shown in (1). One then has: $N y dp/dy + 1.5 p y = 0$ or $N dp/dy + 1.5 p = 0$. ((12))

One may see that $\exp(-y)$ is a solution of ((12)) where $y=e/T$.

This means that:

$$p(e_i/T) p(e_j/T) = p(e_l/T) p(e_k/T) \text{ if } e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l \quad ((13))$$

((13)), however, is reaction balance. Furthermore, given reaction balance for the MB case, we have shown in previous notes that one may obtain a function $F(p)$ such that:

$$d/dp F(p) - 1/T e dp/dp = 0 \text{ i.e. MaxEnt.} \quad ((14))$$

One may readily see that this function is $-p \ln(p)$, i.e. Shannon's entropy. Thus, in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, the scaling of the energy constraint $T \rightarrow T+dT$, yields both reaction balance and MaxEnt. We further note that MaxEnt may be obtained independently by

maximizing $\ln(\text{number of arrangements} = N! / \text{Product over } i \text{ } n(e_i)!) \text{ subject to } \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i n(e_i) = E_{ave}$, where $n(e_i) = N p(e_i)$, if one uses Stirling's approximation: $n \ln(n) = \ln(n!)$.

Scaling of the Energy Constraint and the Tsallis Case

In the Tsallis case, the energy constraint is linked with an unnormalized probability of p power q and not p . The differential equation from scaling is ((6)) and it involves derivatives of y , i.e. d/dy acting on p , with $p(y)$. We note that mathematically, a maximization subject to a constraint also involves derivatives of p . In other words, dp/dy may be seen as the delta p of the maximization approach. In other words, we argue that the maximization approach is very similar to a differential equation approach.

In the maximization case, one may consider a function:

p power q $F(p)$ which is maximized (derivative d/dp) subject to the constraint $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p$ power q ((15))

We note that by writing the function to be maximized as p power q $F(p)$, one obtains two terms when taking d/dp , namely:

$F d/dp (p \text{ power } q)$ and $p \text{ power } q dF/dp$ whereas the constraint yields $-e_i/T d/dp (p \text{ power } q)$ ((16))

This suggests that $F(p) = -e_i/T$ ((17))

((17)), however, means that $F(p)$ is the inverse of p because $p(e_i/T)$. The differential equation from scaling, however, gives the solution for $p(e_i/T)$ namely:

$p(e) = (1 - (1-q) e/T)^{1/(1-q)}$ ((18)).

((18)) is unnormalized and is chosen to yield $p(e) = \exp(-e/T)$ for $q \rightarrow 1$. The scaling approach yields $p(e)$ and so one may use ((17)) to find $F(p)$, namely:

$F(p) = 1/(1-q) (1 - p \text{ power } (1-q))$ if one wants $F(p, q=1) = \ln(p)$ ((19))

One may then check that $dF/dp = 1$. In other words, the MaxEnt procedure can be constructed from the solution of $p(e)$ which is already given by the scaling of the energy constraint approach. As a result, one might view the scaling approach and not MaxEnt as the starting point to determining the Tsallis distribution.

Conclusion

In Parts 1,2 we introduced a scaling of the energy constraint (i.e. $T \rightarrow T+dT$) approach with the coefficient of dT being 0, if $E=T \cdot \text{Number}$. Number is a pure number, but at the same time an integral of functions of e, T and so replacing T with $T+dT$ means that the coefficient of dT must

be 0, We used this approach to derive both the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis distributions without any recourse to MaxEnt, or reaction balance in the MB case.

Here we show that the scaling approach leads to both reaction balance and MaxEnt in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case and to MaxEnt in the Tsallis case. In other words, the more traditional approaches to finding the distributions may be seen to emerge from the scaling of the constraint approach, at least in the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis cases.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Solving for the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution Using Scaling Parts 1 and 2 (preprint, zenodo, 2026)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Scaling Approach to Obtaining the Tsallis Distributions (preprint, zenodo, 2026)